

Urbanisation Impact and Detection of Urban Heat Island in Rome

Matej Hanžek^{1,*}

¹ Graditeljsko geodetska škola Osijek, Osijek, Croatia, mhanzek@geof.hr

* corresponding author

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Abstract: The impact of global warming is increasing and it is one of the main reasons for the rise of temperature and the appearance of urban heat islands. Along with global warming, urbanization and industrialization, processes significantly affect changes in cities and the environment. There is an increasing trend of living in cities and is one of the main reasons for the increase in soil and air temperatures. This research analyses the impact and detection of urban heat islands in the period from 2000 to 2020 in the Rome area based on data collected by the Landsat satellite mission. By conducting a classification of land cover changes and calculating spectral indices within Google Earth Engine and their changes over time, the link between urbanization and the appearance of UHI is showing. This paper shows the need for careful urban planning in order to reduce the impact of urban growth on the ecological system and improve the quality of life.

Keywords: urbanization; land surface temperature (LST); urban heat island (UHI); remote sensing; spectral indices (NDVI, NDBI, MNDWI).

1 Introduction

Land Surface Temperature (LST) is increasing due to global warming, to which urbanization and centralization significantly contribute. Due to the modern way of life, more and more people are moving to urban areas, which is the main cause of centralization in many countries. This process can be influenced by certain political measures, but it is impossible to stop it. Centralization is closely related to the process of urbanization, and they are connected in a certain way. Cities around the world are experiencing a major increase in urban population. Therefore, urbanization is one of the main causes of global warming, climate change and environmental issues (Gašparović et al. 2021). Along with the rapid process of urbanization, the built environment contributes to a significant increase in LST in the urban environment, which accelerates the effect of the Urban Heat Island (UHI) (Mohiuddin and Mund 2024). UHI entails an increase in air temperature that affects people's lives if there are not enough water bodies and areas under vegetation in the urban environment. Observing the entire Earth's surface is unimaginable today without satellite images with an ever-increasing amount of data available to everyone. From a satellite viewpoint, the term surface refers to everything that is observed when looking through the atmosphere to the ground. This observation could include various elements such as snow, ice, grass, building roofs or forest canopies (Mohiuddin and Mund 2024).

The Landsat series of satellites has the potential to provide high spatial resolution LST estimates that are particularly suitable for local and small-scale studies (Ermida et al. 2020). The processing of satellite images is done within

Google Earth Engine, which allows for large-scale data processing, calculations and visualization. The connection of the processes occurring in the subject area with the occurrence of UHI was made using the classification of the subject area, the calculation of vegetation indices and the displays of temperature changes that occur. The paper presents the changes that have occurred in the subject area in the midst of processes that occurred over time. The changes relate to the detection of UHI and the prediction of future changes brought about by global warming, one of the biggest problems of today. UHI occurs in urban areas due to higher concentrations of exhaust gases, the conversion of green areas that reduce warming into built-up areas, and very high building densities.

The changes will be studied by creating a land cover classification of the subject area for a period of 20 years in order to study changes in the area. In addition to the classification, vegetation indices indicating the extent of green areas and soil temperature will be analyzed, along with their prediction based on existing data. The second chapter describes the materials and methods that used, including satellite images and calculation formulas, the third chapter presents the results related to vegetation indices and soil temperature, while the fourth chapter will summarize the study. The main goal of this paper is to use satellite images to determine parameters indicating the occurrence of UHI and make a prediction for the study area. For the detection of UHI, vegetation indices and the classification of the study area will be used, while for prediction, different techniques for locating UHI will be taken into account, to determine whether it is possible to predict the occurrence of UHI.

2 Materials and methods

Considering all the factors influencing the occurrence of UHI, Rome was selected as the study area. Due to its size and population, it serves as a representative example of how national processes, climate change, and human factors affect quality of life. Rome was selected as a case study due to significant changes in population and urban development, making it suitable for analyses over both short and long time. Rome is the capital of Italy, covering an area of 1285 km². According to the 2019 census it has 2837322 inhabitants, making it Italy's most populous municipality. The study area is shown in Figure 1 and includes the city center and surrounding areas. For the purposes of this study, data from the Landsat 5 and Landsat 8 satellite missions were used. Landsat 5 was used to create land cover classification and calculate spectral indices for the year 2000, while Landsat 8 was used for 2020.

Figure 1. Overview of the subject area – City of Rome.

Classifications using the random forest algorithm will show changes in the extent of urban areas in relation to the vegetation, while spectral index calculations will be used to detect urban heat islands. The vegetation indices that will be calculated are: Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI), Normalized Difference Built-up Index (NDBI) and Modified Normalized Difference Water Index (MNDWI), and the calculation is made according to equation 1-3:

$$NDVI = \frac{NIR - Red}{NIR + Red} \quad (1)$$

$$NDBI = \frac{SWIR - NIR}{SWIR + NIR} \quad (2)$$

$$MNDWI = \frac{GREEN - SWIR}{GREEN + SWIR} \quad (3)$$

3 Results and discussions

The results for the subject area are presented in this chapter. Over a period of 20 years, due to the process of urbanization and changes occurring in society, the population has increased by 548,755 inhabitants. Based on census data, the population of Rome is growing by 1% of the total population annually, and the number of inhabitants over the years is shown in Figure 2.

Due to climate change and changes within the city itself, the average temperature has increased by 1.8 °C over a 20-year period (Figure 3). The data was taken from observations of meteorological stations within Rome.

Land cover maps were created using supervised classification within GEE. Land cover maps were created based on three classes: water, urban area and vegetation area, every class had 10 samples.

Figure 2. The number of inhabitants of Rome in the period from 2000 to 2020.

Figure 4 shows some of the factors contributing to the increase in temperatures in the study area. A large portion of the area in the southeast and southwest part of the city that was previously covered by vegetation has been converted into built-up areas due to increased housing demand driven by population growth. In addition to land cover classifications and statistical analyses of population and temperature, graphical representations of spectral indices were also generated. These include NDVI (Normalized Difference Vegetation Index), indicating vegetation presence, NDBI (Normalized Difference Built-up Index), indicating built-up areas, and MNDWI (Modified Normalized Difference Water Index) indicating water bodies. All results are displayed from red indicating minimum results to blue indicating maximum results. The range of results for all three spectral indices shown in Figure 5, Figure 6 and Figure 7. The analyses is based on spatiotemporal data collected between 2000 to 2020. In the subject area, with the increase in temperature, the proportion of green areas has decreased, as indicated by the NDVI index. The MNDWI index, i.e. the share of water areas, has also decreased, which is closely related to the increased NDBI index, i.e. the increased share of built-up areas. The values of the NDVI index range from -0.010 to 0.450, NDBI from -0.310 to 0.030 and MNDWI from -0.150 to 0.180. All the results shown in Table 1. confirm that the process of urbanization greatly influenced the creation of UHI in Rome. A comparison of the results of the calculated spectral indices, the created classification and the satellite images mutually confirm the presented results. The trend of the emergence of UHI in megalopolises is also confirmed in the area of Rome in changes in land cover, number of people and graphical representations that indicate this made within GEE.

Figure 3. Comparison of temperatures in 2000 (left image) and 2020 (right image). (Weather Spark 2020).

Figure 4. Land cover classification for Rome for the years (left) 2000 and (right) 2020. Built-up area is shown in red, vegetation in green, and water in blue.

Figure 5. NDVI index for the year 2000 (left image) and 2020 (right image) for the subject area with legend.

Figure 6. NDBI index for the year 2000 (left image) and 2020 (right image) for the subject area with legend.

Figure 7. MNDWI index for the year 2000 (left image) and 2020 (right image) for the subject area with legend.

Table 1. Final results for classifications and spectral indices calculations.

Final results		
Classification	Year 2000	Year 2020
Built-up area	13643,82 km ²	14251,11 km ²
Vegetation	9220,21 km ²	8527,08 km ²
Water	120,23 km ²	206,06 km ²
Spectral indices	Year 2000	Year 2020
mean NDVI	0,198	0,230
mean NDBI	-0,151	-0,195
mean MNDWI	0,031	0,025

4 Conclusions

The aim of this research is to analyze the changes that occurred between 2000 and 2020 in Rome and to determine whether they influenced the occurrence of heat islands. The process of urbanization drives changes in natural landscapes, environmental degradation and an increase in built-up areas. The analysis was carried out through the correlation of three spectral indices NDVI, NDBI and MNDWI, LST and by classification of downloaded images. The research presents a simple methodology for testing the occurrence of UHI in megalopolises. All graphical outputs and satellite image processing were performed using GEE.

Land cover analysis indicates rapid urban growth accompanied by a loss of vegetation areas. Land cover analysis along with vegetation indices (NDVI, NDBI, MNDWI) confirm the trend of urbanization with the occurrence of heat islands. The correlation between spectral indices, LST and land cover classification is strong in this study, and they confirm that the process of urbanization interacts with the increase of built-up areas, the reduction of water and green areas. The subject area is an example of inadequate adaptation to the impacts of urbanization, considering the rates of change and the results presented using spectral indices.

The methodology used in this study based on multi temporal satellite analysis is widely applicable and highly

adaptable. In order to reduce certain limitations and increase the reliability of the results, it is necessary to take into account local factors. The study contributes to urban planning policy and insight into the current state. To maintain the ecosystem in the future, it is necessary to pay attention to reducing the rate of temperature increase in urban planning. An extension of this study would be the use of more spectral indices with local factors taken into account and the prediction of the rate of temperature increase and the occurrence of UHI.

5 References

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